

THE ROLES OF THE TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN THE INTEGRATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH

Achilova Ra'no Tashpo'latovna

Abstract With the spread of English as a lingua franca and as the medium for world-wide broadcasting of information and knowledge, in many cases, the pragmatic objectives of language learning emphasize the importance of integrated language skill teaching and flexible instruction. In general, insight on current language curriculum, teaching reading is typically associated to instruction on writing and vocabulary, teaching writing can be easily tied to reading and grammar, and speaking skills readily lend the learners to teaching listening, pronunciation, and cross-cultural pragmatics. In connection to this, Shen, (2003) confirms that the implementation of language in communication, should closely integrates linguistic competence with communicative skills and communicative culture in the process of language skill teaching so that the learners' linguistic competence and their communicative skills can be improved simultaneously. These had to be interaction-centered and as authentic as possible to enable students to use the language skills for purposeful and effective communication. To achieve the envisioned objectives of the integrative language teaching approach, both students are expected to play different roles.

Furthermore, the effective practices of the integrative language skills teaching in the classroom may be challenged by different factors. Hence, the factors should be identified and addressed to effectively use the integrative approach to language skills teaching. In connection to this, the main purposes of this review article was to describe the roles of the teachers and students in integrative language teaching approach and to present the factors that affect the practice of this approach. To achieve this objectives various, books, book chapters, guidelines, research findings and documents were critically reviewed and analyzed. Accordingly, this review

article describes the roles of the teachers and students in integrative language skill teaching approach. In addition, it presents the major factors that affect the practices of the integrative language skills teaching approach.

Keywords: Teachers, Students , Integrative, Language, Teaching Approach, Factors, Use , Actual Classroom

Introduction

An integrative approach is the approach of teaching language skills simultaneously. This means the four macro skills (reading, writing, speaking, and listening) are taught concurrently. Richards and Rogers (2001) define it as “integrated language skills teaching approach is “the teaching of the language skills of reading, writing, listening, and speaking in conjunction with each other as when a lesson involves activities that relate listening and speaking to reading and writing.” According to Afnan, (2014), integrating language teaching approach is vital technique for effective language learning. This technique refers to including two or more than two language skills, in a lesson/ task. Richards and Schmidt (2010) as cited in Afnan 2014 also define this approach as relating reading, writing, speaking, and listening together in activity that can be taught via a holistic method. Integrating language skills teaching can be described as a whole-language approach or a multi-skill syllabus. This is because the approach teaches all the language skills together.

Definition of Authentic Materials

Integrated language skills teaching approach is a whole language approach. That is, if a lesson deals with reading skills, then, it will also deal with listening, speaking, and writing skills. It emphasizes on communication purpose in addition to academic success (Hungyo and Kijai 2009 as cited in Elena and Lorena 2011). The four English language skills can be taught integratively in the actual classroom situation via integrative approach. For example, by practicing conversational skills the learner can focus not only on speaking but also listening, in order to reply and ask appropriate follow-up questions. All language skills are considered and to be essential components to develop the communicative competence of students, the

skills should be taught together via interactive language teaching approach. Thus, the approach advocates integration of all language skills in actual classroom situation (Crystal, 2003). In other words, integrated language skill teaching approach is the natural way of learning a language. In real life communication, language skills are rarely used in isolation; it is a rare situation where one of the four skills occurs alone. For example, to engage in a conversation, one needs to be able to speak and comprehend at the same time (Jing, 2006).

In terms of integration skill Oxford (2001) introduces the concept of tapestry, it is woven from different strands including the teacher, learner, setting, and relevant languages besides four skills. She believed that absence of such threads may lead to a discrete, segregated skills-like in a real tapestry parallel threads not touching, supporting, or interacting with each other. Additionally she argue that in integrative language skill teaching includes associated or related skills such as knowledge of vocabulary, spelling, pronunciation, syntax, meaning, and usage. According to her, this forms an integrated language teaching approach.

In effective lessons language teachers must be integrate language skills simultaneously in order to make language learning as realistic as possible which is a requisite in communication. Often one skill will reinforce another; we learn to speak, for example, in part by modeling what we hear, and we learn to write by examining what we can read (Brown, 2001). For instance, teaching reading can be easily tied to instruction on writing and vocabulary, and oral skills readily lend themselves to teaching pronunciation, listening, and cross-cultural pragmatics (Hinkel, 2001; Lazaraton, 2001; McCarthy and O'Keeffe, 2004). Furthermore, other scholars confirm that language learning tasks should be designed in an integrative manner (McDonough and Shaw, 2003).

This helps students to be involved in language tasks that integrate different language skills and advance their skills (Hulstijn and Laufer, 2001). Moreover, educators (such as Fotos, 2002; Ellis, 2003; Snow, 2005) argue that integrative language skill instruction can increase learners opportunities for language learning

and purposeful communication, interaction, real-life language use and diverse types of contextualized discourse and linguistic features, all of which have the goal of developing students language proficiency and skills. When the four primary skills of language: listening, reading, speaking and writing are interwoven during instruction, it helps us emulate real-life language use and it also paves the way for optimal language learning to take place (Oxford, 2001). In addition to this purposes, integration of four skills can develop communicative competence, because the real life demands from the learners not only immersion into the knowledge of language, but also into the knowledge about how to use the language appropriately in communicative situations (Jing,2006).

From the above discussion, it can understand that integrated language teaching skill approach is the usual way of learning a language and allows teachers to track students' progress in multiple skills at the same time. Integration of language skills will expose learners to actual language use and encourage interaction (Oxford, 2001). Furthermore, there are several advantages of using integrative approach to teach language skills.

Integrating the four skills emphasizes the focus on realistic language and can, therefore, develops learners communicative competence in English (Jing, 2006). Nunan(1989) believes that integration of language skills is very important to every day communication, language teaching_ learning process and task outcomes. (Schurr et al, 1995) established that the language use is holistic in the real world, this demands from the Language teachers to provide learners with an environment where they can immerse in reading, writing, speaking and listening.

According to Hungyo and Kijai (2009) as cited in Elena and Lorena (2011) stated that one of the advantages of using this approach is that teachers can prepare the lesson plan around a theme or a topic based on the interest of learners and also on topics that are relevant to them which contributes to make lessons more dynamic and attractive for learners, who participate in different kinds of activities and discussion. But according to Oxford (2001) as cited in Elena and Lorena (2011) one

of the most advantages of using the integrated language teaching approach is that it exposes English language learners to authentic language and challenges them to interact naturally in the language. She also comments that exposing students to communicative situation helps and empower to them of the richness and complexity of the English language.

Conclusion

In this approach a teacher has the responsibilities of organizing varies kinds of activities which are appropriate, effective and relevant to the teaching of language skills and which will best meet the students' needs and expectations. The teacher should give clear instructions as to what to be done because the success of many activities, no matter whether it is a specific role-play or a group discussion, depends on good organization and on the students knowing exactly what they are expected to do. Teacher's role as manager and organizer is considered to be the first and foremost role teacher has to play in the class (Shanghais, 2012).

On the other hand, in integrative language skill teaching approach, teachers are not the only source of language information in these days of global interconnectedness, and the language teachers should understand that students need to develop strategies to respond and adapt to changes rather than approaching the task of language learning in a uniform way (Warschauer and Healey, 1998). They also believe that the teacher should play the role of facilitator rather than being the source of knowledge.

Moreover, language teachers should take the responsibilities to integrate language skills through different mechanisms like organizing the learners in groups, to select appropriate materials that must be much with in this approach, create awareness towards integrative approach and etc.

References

1. Afnan,M.(2014), Kumaravadivelu's Framework as a Basis for Improving English Language Teaching in Saudi Arabia: Opportunities and Challenges: Vol. 7, No. 4; Canadian Center of Science and Education.

2. Almarza, S, M. A.(2000). An Approach to Integration of Skills in English Teaching; *Didactica (Lengua y Literatura)* : pp.21-44
3. Arslan, A.(2008). Implementing a Holistic Teaching in Modern ELT Classes: Using Technology and Integrating Four Skills :Naval Training Center.
4. Brown, H.D. (2001). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language*. Pedagogy 2nd Ed., Newyork: Pearson Education.
5. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Service Parts of Speech as an Important Component of Advertising Text in Russian and Uzbek Languages (By the Material of Advertising in the Sphere of Medicine). *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 3, 1-7.
6. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). DISCOURSE ABOUT THE PECULIARITIES OF THE THEME OF MALE GENDER IN ADVERTISING TEXTS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK (ON THE MATERIAL OF MEDICAL VOCABULARY). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(2), 4-8.
7. ГАНИЕВ, Б., & Ганиева, М. С. (2019). Религиозно-исламские и духовные корни предпринимательской деятельности в Средней Азии. In *ИДЕАЛЫ И ЦЕННОСТИ ИСЛАМА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ XXI ВЕКА* (pp. 332-335).
8. Makhmudova, N. R. (2019). The use of multimedia learning tools in the English language. *Мировая наука*, (9), 44-48.
9. Abbasova, N. K. (2018). Using Effective Techniques Developing Learners' Critical Thinking in Teaching English Proverbs and Sayings. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (6).
10. Maxmudova, N. (2022). PRAGMATIC SIGNS OF ORNITHONYMS IN PROVERBS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 88-91.
11. Qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINICIPLES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).
12. Do'smatov, D. qizi Shodiyeva, GN (2022, May). O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH.